

Waterproofing the VAISALA WXT520 or WXT530

Materials needed:

- Damaged WXT unit.
- New WXT unit.
- Clear Silicone Sealant cartridge with caulking gun.
- Corrosion X (HD) spray can (<http://www.corrosionx.com/corrosionx-heavy-duty.html>) or equivalent.
- MG Encapsulation and potting epoxy kit (<http://www.mgchemicals.com/products/potting-compounds/epoxy-potting-compounds/translucent-epoxy-832c>) or equivalent.
- Type 316 Stainless Steel Fully Threaded Rod M4 Thread, 0.7mm Pitch, 500mm <https://www.mcmaster.com/#94185a582/=17qmkfr> . Cut to 3x130-mm long rods.
- (3x) 18-8 Stainless Steel Coupling Nut - M4 x 0.7 mm Thread <https://www.mcmaster.com/#93590A104>
- (1x) O-ring 1/16 Fractional Width, Dash Number 014 <https://www.mcmaster.com/#9452k58/=17qmmut>
- Several syringes.

Potting compounds can be replaced by:

*<https://www.mcmaster.com/7467A274/>

*<https://www.mcmaster.com/6430A27/>

1. Take apart the WXT520 or WXT530 bottom part.

- Remove the three long screws with allen wrench.
- Disconnect the flat ribbon cable from bottom board.
- Remove the board from the shield:
 - Remove three small screws.
 - Remove the flat nut from the unused small circular connector.
- Remove black rubber joint.
- Keep gray rubber caps in place.
- Keep pigtail connector in place.
- Keep stainless-steel cylinder in place.

Sun shields

Stainless steel cylinder

Pigtail connector

Twist and lock mount

Gray rubber cap

Long screws

Small screws

Unused small connector and its nut

Black rubber joint

1. Take apart the WXT520 or WXT530 top part.

2. Differences between WXT520 and WXT 530

WXT520

WXT530

WXT530 has an extra metallic cover inside the top part

Shape and pinout on the bottom board differ.

3. Waterproof pigtail connector and stainless steel cylinder.

While the pigtail connector is preventing water to come in, water can still come in at the very bottom (red arrows) where the WXT5X0 is mounted on the twist and lock mount which is connected to the mast of the Waveglider.

- With the pigtail connector, the stainless-steel cylinder, and the twist and lock mount installed, inject silicone at the base of the pigtail connector (blue arrow) and in the spaces between the stainless-steel cylinder and the shield (orange arrows).
- Tip: apply grease on the lock legs (pink arrows) of the twist and lock mount, so the silicone does not stick to them. This helps when removing the twist and lock connector from the bottom part when the silicone becomes dry.

4. Unsolder the unused circular connector from the bottom board

This connector is not used.
Removing it helps later on when the
board is potted with epoxy resin.

5. Waterproofing the electronics of the top board.

- Inject potting epoxy compound into the underside recesses for the three small posts that house the sonic transducers until the compound overflows.
- Once the epoxy is dry, spray CorrosionX on the electronics board, letting it run over to immerse both sides of the board.
- Wait an hour or so, then flip the assembly over so the excess spray can drip out of the top part.

5. Waterproofing the electronics of the top board.

- Remove the stickers on the top lid (optional).
- Reinsert the lid on the top part, with the flat ribbon cable plugged in; don't forget to reset the large O-ring around the base of the lid.
- Reinstall the 3 small screws.
- Unlike how it is shown in the pictures, keep the black rubber piece around the flat ribbon cable and out of its housing.

6. Waterproofing the temperature, humidity and pressure (THP) sensor

- Replace the flat washer gasket with close fit O-ring.

- Reinstall the THP sensor in place.
- Apply a thick layer of silicone all over the housing of the THP sensor.

- Apply silicone at the base of the cap .

7. Sealing the top part

- Inject epoxy into tapped screw threads then install the three 4-mm rods

- Install the first sun shield and keep injecting epoxy on top of the lid until the junction between the lid and the top part is completely sealed.

- Inject silicone inside the housing of the rubber piece around the flat ribbon cable.
- Inject silicone on both sides of the flat ribbon cable.

7. Seal top part

- Slide the rubber piece down into its housing and add more silicone between the flat ribbon cable and the rubber piece (both sides).

- Stack all the sun shields around the 3 rods and the flat ribbon cable.
- Add the last part (which is the lid of the bottom part).
- Tighten down the entire assembly using the 4mm nuts.

- Make sure the flat cable housing fits well in its mating part, and that silicone overflows from this connection.

8. Preparation of bottom part for potting

- Cover the hole of the unsoldered connector with tape.
- Enlarge the diameter of the 3 holes (orange arrows) so the 4mm rod freely fits inside them.

- These 3 holes need to be temporarily filled so epoxy resin won't drain through them.

- From a broken WXT, cut off the cylinders shown with the pink arrows.
- Rub them with O-ring grease, then mount them in their mating position and tighten them down with 4mm screws (blue arrows) from the opposite face.

9. Potting the bottom part.

- Reinsert the flat ribbon cable into the bottom board.
- Lay down the top part of the WXT higher than the bottom part to keep the bottom part stable and horizontal during the pouring process.
- Level the bottom part as best as possible.
- Connect back the pigtail wires to the electronics board terminal connectors.
- Keep the board elevated, so that you can pour epoxy resin underneath it.
- Pour the resin until it reaches the top of the 3 small standoffs (pink arrows).

If the unused connector has not been unsoldered, tighten down the board with the 3 small screws and the unused connector nut before pouring the epoxy resin.

- Bring the board down onto the standoffs, fastening it down with the 3 small screws.
- Resume pouring resin until it reaches the top edge of the outer slot.

Don't let the resin overflow past the top edge of the outer slot into the O-ring groove!!

- If the bottom part is properly levelled, all parts of the board should be covered by resin except for the green terminal connector.
- Let it dry.

10. Closing of the WXT

- Grind one side of the three 4-mm nuts (blue arrows on the right) so they can fit their housings (pink arrows)

- Apply silicone in the O-ring slot and the 3 screw holes. Don't use the O-ring, reconnect the bottom and top parts together, and tighten them together with the three 4mm nuts.
- Cover the 4mm nuts with a thick layer of silicone.

11. Waterproofing the rain cover.

- Use flexible plastic sheeting to create a cylindrical barrier between the rain cover and the three small posts that house the wind speed transducers. I used the plastic cylinder that usually comes with a new WXT520 (I am not sure if the WXT530 comes with this piece).
- Tape it down to the WXT so that the resin won't drip away. Go heavy on the tape !!
- Pour resin between the plastic barrier and the rain cover.
- Let it dry.
- Remove the plastic sheet and tape.
- If needed, grind the outside edge of the solid resin ring.

ALL DONE

